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Developing new means for monitoring the strategical goals implemented in public procurement: A machine learning approach

Arash Hajikhani, Juha Oksanen and Maria Merisalo

Introduction

Public procurement has become an important policy tool for implementing the strategic goals of public bodies (e.g. European Commission 2021; Glas et al. 2017; Uyarra et al. 2020). This is because a massive amount of public money is used for public procurement yearly, e.g. in European Union the yearly spending corresponds 14 % of GDP (European Commission 2020). Strategical policy goals, often related to innovation and sustainability, aim to positively impact, e.g., markets, the environment, or social sustainability (Sönnichsen & Clement 2020; Uyarra & Flanagan 2010).

Extensive societal impacts are achieved when the masses of individual procurements acknowledge the strategical goals and are implemented in a manner supporting these aims. In practice, public bodies have the role and power of including certain criteria supporting sustainability or conducting procurements in a way that leaves space for new solutions to emerge (e.g. Edquist & Zabala-Iturriagoitia 2012).

Regardless of the increase in including strategical goals (for achieving certain impacts) into the procurement, the means to monitor the progress have lagged behind. In fact, new means to monitor the progress of public procurement promoting such goals are needed in order for public bodies to get accurate knowledge of the progress at national, regional and organizational levels (Grandia & Meehan 2017). Tender documents provide an interesting data source to be used as those include the required procurement specific information for the monitoring. The potential is enormous as tendering documents could be used to form new "big data" sources to be utilized in the monitoring. At the moment, there are very few benchmarks presented in the literature on this topic (PwC 2020).

This article fills the gap by developing new means for monitoring the increase of public procurement, including strategical goals. Our aim is to develop a new machine learning method that recognizes the public procurements that either include 1) the so-called "employment criteria" aiming for increasing the employment rate and giving opportunities for trainee positions for young people, or 2) the so-called "SME-criteria" aiming to increase the participation of small and medium-size enterprises in delivering public procurement. In order to develop the method, we conduct a case study by utilizing the tender documents of the city of Espoo (in Finland) for two years period.

The article is structured as follows: First, we elaborate on the overall evaluation process and data involved in a public procurement process. Then we continue positioning our entry point

for evaluation practice which is on tender level documents. Second, we introduce our text analytics approach in systematically analyzing the tender documents and establishing the research design for automating and expanding such a process. Third, we apply our methodological approach to the case study, implementing all the steps to arrive at a production machine learning-based criteria identification model. Finally, we deliver our findings and immediate results by applying the ML model to the case study. In the end, we discuss our research additionality and introduce further research avenues.

Public Procurement Process Evaluation

Evaluation of the strategical goals and eventually related impacts of public procurement calls for a framework that recognizes the multi-phase nature of procurement practice. The procurement process consists of sequential activities, and there are different types of information sources and data available in different stages to consider in the framework.

The procurement cycle starts with the assessment of the needs the procuring agency aims to address through procurement. In some cases, the needs can be well articulated in advance (e.g. if the question is about a routine stocking up with commonly consumed items), while in other needs can be less articulated or even unique requiring more predefinition. Closely related to needs assessment is information gathering and market scanning activities to map broadly if existing products, services or solutions available on the market match the needs of the procuring agency. Needs definition as well as information and market scanning type of activities are important elements of the preparation and planning phase. As our focus is on (impact) evaluation of public procurement, we refer to this phase by term 'pre-evaluation'/'ex-ante evaluation' in this paper (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Public procurement evaluation phases

Tendering phase in the procurement process can be understood to cover the publication of call for tenders, selection and evaluation of tenders/bids, and award of the contract. Legislation for public procurement sets strict demands on the process in this phase, such as rules and requirements for procurement practices, procedures applied, and publicity of the calls. In this study, we use data from this part of the procurement cycle to develop and test a text analytics-based approach to assess to which extent specific strategic goals (i.e. employment or SME criteria) are considered/aimed at in public procurement.

The third part of the cycle relates to managing the contract, ensuring that performance and goals set for the contract are met, and possibly also preparing to launch a new procurement process for a new contract period. This phase is termed as 'post-evaluation'/'ex-post evaluation' in our framework and is extended to cover the period after the contract is accomplished to enable ex-post analysis of impacts.

Depending on the phase in the procurement cycle, certain evaluation relevant data sources and data points can be identified. In the pre-evaluation/ex-ante evaluation phase, various sources are available and used. Internal guidelines, such as strategy documents and interaction and dialogue between internal procurement experts and staff presenting substance domain – and with users of public services- are essential information sources for the needs assessment. Experiences and analytic evaluation-based findings (if available) from previous procurements and contracts also feed into preparation and planning. Market scanning activities in this phase help to zoom out and identify a range of potential solutions/alternatives on the market or still in development that could deliver in relation to the need behind procurement.

In the tendering phase, published calls for tenders and accompanied documentation constitute, in principle, a ready-made data set to analyze and assess the presence and integration of strategic goals into actual tenders. The calls published include tender specifications as separate attachments, such as a more detailed definition of the subject of the procurement, inclusion/exclusion and award criteria applied, definition of requirements, deadline for bids, and time frames for delivery of contracted services. The calls for tenders with attached documents are nowadays published and available in online tender portals (such as EU TED portal for calls above the EU thresholds and/or national portals above national thresholds). This type of calls for tenders data and machine learning methodology were used by PwC team in a recent benchmarking study assessing the volume of public procurement on innovative solutions in Europe (European Commission 2021b).

It is worth noting that the tender documents, while a valuable source for procurement data, primarily sheds light on explicit expressed aims and intentions linked with public procurement but not yet on impacts sought-after and unfolding in process during and after the contract delivery. This leads us to the third phase in the procurement cycle and the designed evaluation framework. The aim of the Post-evaluation/ex-post evaluation is to assess what type of intended and (unintended) impacts procurement(s) have had (e.g., regarding strategic goals, quality of public services and innovation/supplier companies' success).

Text analytics in exploring procurement announcements

In general due to digitization the amount of unstructured data is increasing rapidly and the need for automated means to process it is growing. Text Mining (T.M.) - also known as Text Data Mining (TDM) or Knowledge Discovery in Text (KDT) is the automated process of translating large volumes of unstructured text into quantitative data to uncover insights, trends, and patterns (Aggarwal & Zhai 2013; Delgado et al. 2002).

The tender documentation and amendments present a set of unstructured documents of various types (pdf, doc, docx, ppt, etc.) that partly use an arbitrarily defined structure. However, the contents must include information related to the eligible conditions, selection criteria, estimated price, technical and professional capacities, and the type of procedure in the documentation. Detection models, or prediction algorithms, are used to process the textual content. Almost all EU member states have increased the amount of their total budgets that they spend using the public procurement procedures (PwC 2020). The increase in the

importance of these processes both for economic activity and the perspective of the business potential for suppliers led to the adoption of big data techniques and principles in the PPP domain (DG GROW 2017).

Detecting quality and essential information is a crucial part of any data analysis process, especially when it comes to complex models. Bearing in mind that most procurement documents present unstructured data, it is vital to find mechanisms through which this required data can be extracted from the text, especially if it is an automated process. Research looked at evaluating the public procurement process for improving procurement patterns' visibility and providing decision-makers with insight to develop more efficient sourcing strategies (Tan & Lee 2015). Previous text mining and machine learning attempts had been made on public procurement data to detect patterns for fraud detection (Byrne 2013; Fazekas et al. 2016; Rabuzin & Modrušan 2019), sustainable public procurement (J. (Jolien) Grandia & Kruyen 2020; Wang et al. 2018) and innovative solutions in public procurement in the digital economy (PwC 2020).

In this study, we do see the opportunity for experimenting with Finnish public procurement data for multiple reasons 1) Offering a systematic procedure for structuring and preparation of textual content data 2) Working with historical data and creating aggregation points for analytics 3) Provide future path and perspective for Finnish public procurement data analysis.

Research Design

In order to achieve the abovementioned objectives, we performed a case study by using text mining and ML methods to identify clusters of call for tenders including specific (strategic) goals that a procurement agency desires to achieve through procurements. Here we were interested in following selected goals:

1. Employment through procurement ("employment criteria"). Procurement agencies have increasingly started to use so called employment criteria in order to increase employment through procurement(s). In practice, the agency obligates the supplier to include for example an unemployed person or a person with partial work capacity into the delivered work (e.g. Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, 2020; Troje & Kadefors, 2018).
2. Increasing SME participation in delivering public procurements ("SME criteria"). Small and medium size enterprises' success rates in delivering public procurement are lower in comparison to their contribution to GDP (European Commission, 2020). Thus, some public procurement agencies have started to include SME perspective in their procurement preparation in order to ensure that also SMEs have a possibility to respond to call for tender (e.g. acknowledge procurement size or allow tenders only for some specific part of the call).

Our aim was to make models that automatically recognizes those calls for tenders that include such goals. The four-stage process for tender data retrieval, data transformation, introductory text harmonizing, data structuring and expansion is illustrated in Figure 2.

This study aims to demonstrate how advanced data mining techniques combined with supervised machine learning methods can be used to improve the visibility of procurement patterns. A case study of Espoo city procurement data will be processed and presented in this report. The following section will dive into utilizing the tender transformed data for training a machine learning model for detecting specific criteria within tender documents.

Figure 2. Tender data transformation and preparation for analyzing

Case study: A pilot study with Espoo city procurement announcements

For the pilot study, we negotiated with Cloudia (digital procurement sourcing service) for the possibility to utilize data that is gathered into their data repository. In compliance with the city of Espoo and Ministry of Finance we agreed that Cloudia transferred for the project (for VTT) Espoo city procurement data (call for tender related documents) covering time period 1.1.2018 - 31.11.2020. Permission for the transfer was received from Espoo and cost (for the transfer) covered for Cloudia. The data arrived at VTT securely in two batches. The first batch was an excel file containing the overall metadata regarding a tender such as Id, short description, etc. The second batch of over 20 G.B. had tenders' documents in folder structure where each folder includes the annexes for the tender (documents in .pdf, .doc format). In total, the tenders with all annexes counted to be 1128 folders which contain 7518 documents. Next, all folders name and their subfiles that includes the tender Ids and the document names were mapped to a flat-file (similar to excel sheet). This step enabled us to verify in case we have the metadata for the tenders available in the excel sheet as well. Python programming language and packages was used to retrieve files (mainly pdfs) into text to advance text analytics. The preliminary cleaning procedures such as space removal, non-character removal performed in text fields. In all the steps, we maintained the unique identifiers for each file to track it to the tender document and to be able later to expand the data set if needed. An additional data was provided by Espoo city regarding the tenders that complied with either employment or SME criteria. We used this data further in training the machine learning model.

Now the data is in the format to experiment in training and compile a machine learning model for scaling and automating the tender identification. The defined criteria (Employment and SME) are visible. Figure 3 is sketching the process stepwise.

We used the Python programming language and relevant packages to perform the process. In pre-processed tender's text the tabular structure data where each tender's textual content is harmonized into text block was taken as input data. In Text preparation for ML model task parsed the textual content into tokens. Tokenization was essentially splitting a phrase, sentence, paragraph, or entire text document into smaller units, such as individual words or terms. The tokens were purified from stop words. Examples of stop words in English are "a", "the", "is", "are" and etc however we utilized the Finnish language packages for taking the Finnish language stop words out of the tokens. Feature extraction was an essential step as it performs particular treatment and transformation to convert the textual content to their numerical representations. In our case, we relied on the TF-IDF method, which stands for term frequency-inverse document frequency for tokens transformation which is very useful for scoring words in machine learning algorithms for Natural Language Processing (NLP). TF-IDF was a statistical measure that evaluates how relevant a word is to a document in a

collection of documents. This was done by multiplying two metrics: how many times a word appears in a document, and the inverse document frequency of the word across a set of documents. The statistic TF-IDF was intended to measure how important a word was to a document in a collection (or corpus) of documents, for example, to one novel.

Figure 3. Machine learning model construction for automated criteria detecting in tender texts

To put it in more formal mathematical terms, the TF-IDF score for the word t in the document d from the document set D was calculated as follows:

$$tf\ idf(t, d, D) = tf(t, d) \cdot idf(t, D)$$

Where:

$$tf(t, d) = \log(1 + freq(t, d))$$

$$idf(t, D) = \log\left(\frac{N}{count(d \in D: t \in d)}\right)$$

The final product of TF-IDF was a score for each word in document between 0 to 1 if the word was ubiquitous and appeared in many documents, this number approached 0. Otherwise, it approached 1.

Results

In the feature designing phase, authors performed in-depth evaluation of the tender's text. While we knew the tenders complying with criteria, yet the exact wording criteria was not known in the text. We read the tenders text and pinpointed the paragraph and important compound words that could be interpreted essentially in communicating the requirements. Integration of our to feature building was an iterative process as the bag of words trimmed to contain more major and essential phrases. Table 1 in the Annexes shows the our suggested keywords and the frequency of occurrence in the documents.

The keyword's visibility across 1016 full text retrieved project for employment criteria was 121 and for SME criteria 650. On the document level where we had 7519 pdfs, employment criteria were seen in 223 documents and SME criteria in 1690 documents. We used this

knowledge for tagging our files and utilized them in training and test set splitting in the machine learning modeling phase.

Classification Algorithms in Machine Learning is a vast domain and most common algorithms in machine learning are Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes Classifier, K-Nearest Neighbors, Decision Tree, Random Forest and Support Vector Machines. In this experiment we proceeded with random forest algorithm. Random forest is one of the most used algorithms because of flexibility and diversity (it can be used for both classification and regression tasks). The random forest is a classification algorithm that builds multiple decision trees and merges them together to get a more accurate and stable prediction.

In the ML Modeling phase, the train-test split procedure is used to estimate machine learning algorithms' performance when used to make predictions on data not used to train the model. We used Python's scikit-learn machine learning library to perform the train-test split procedure. As the classes were not balanced in quantity, the stratified sampling method was utilized for a desirable split in test and training set.

Then we fitted the model to make predictions and evaluated the predictions using the classification accuracy performance metric. Finally, the model was evaluated on the test set and the performance of the model when making predictions on new data has an accuracy of the model is almost 100%.

SME criteria model: Precision: 0.994 / Recall: 0.941 / Accuracy: 0.991

Employment criteria model: Precision: 1.0 / Recall: 0.956 / Accuracy: 0.999

The reason for the model's high accuracy is that we used the experts extracted keywords as features in the model fitting process; therefore, the model is quite accurate in identifying any tender which contains the expert's keywords. In Annexes Table 2 the ranked feature importance for each model is presented.

Discussion and Conclusion

We utilized public procurement announcements full data (received from local data provider Cloudia) to evaluate the tenders compliance on criteria's such as employment and SME. Conceptualizing and defining the criterias was done by collecting expert's evaluation. Then, we developed text analytics methods to automate case identification in which the defined criteria are visible. By observing the shortlisted announcements that met the specified criteria, we proceeded to compile a training set (Review process) for Machine Learning (ML) modelling. Developing and testing the algorithm automatically searched the text data set and recognized the announcements that have filled the criteria was the end product. Now the model can identify a compliancy of a new tender document regarding Employment and SME requirements.

The modeling performance could be enhanced with other techniques such as word embedding methods. This requires accessing a global Finnish language model. Our pilot experience was a forceful feature design and machine learning modeling as features directly came from experts. More in-depth feature designing could get deep into the language structure of tender texts, and by knowing the criteria, it would be possible to extract other wording structures affiliated to a specific criterion. This requires having trained and test data in a much larger quantity.

Yet, the gained knowledge of tender's compliance with a specific criterion is limited to tender documentation. The exercise can be extended to prior and posterior data on companies' activities, companies' financial status, companies' innovation and R&D to identify the public procurer fund in initiating actions that are compliant with the criteria. These additional data could be fetched from companies' websites, their annual reports, financial data of companies and companies' publication and patenting activities. Extension on data coverage in time horizon, quantity, and location would enable comparative analysis between regions, across time and nations (other EU states).

We were able to demonstrate a pathway for evaluating a part of procurement process which adds value to the impact measurement of the overall procurement process. The research design was able to learn from few examples in extrapolating the criteria identification in a wider set of tender documents. Yet we like to propose some avenues for further research. In the pilot study keywords were defined by the researchers familiar with public procurement. Accuracy of bag of words used would benefit procurement experts' involvement in definition and iteration of keywords. Legal requirements for tender documents are strict and the documents tend to follow standard structures with recurring elements and formulations. An insider view on tender preparation would help to improve relevance of keyword lists and recognize parts of the tender documentation containing relevant information. The latter would require that the text data is arranged in structured format following the structure used in tender documentation.

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Annexes

Table 1. Expert's specified keywords frequency in tender text

Employment Criteria		SME Criteria	
Keyword	Occurrence	Keyword	Occurrence
palkkatuki	607	Jaettu (new: "hankinta on jaettu" and/or "hankinnan kohde on jaettu")	641
palkkatukityöllistämisen kuvaus	425	mikroyritys	555
työllistämisen	356	pieni tai keskisuuri yritys	274
työllistäminen	270	kevennetty kilpailutus	192
heikossa työmarkkina-asemassa	110	minikilpailutus	172
työllistämistoimet	94	tilata suoraan	18
tarjoamaan työpaikan	86	dynaaminen toimittajarekisteri	17
oppisopimuskoulutukseen	84	kertahankinta	16
työllistämään	83	tarjota yhteen	6
oikeutettuja palkkatukeen	81		
työttömiä	79		
työttömiksi työnhakijoiksi	69		
oikeutettu palkkatukeen	30		
työttömäksi työnhakijaksi	28		
hankinnoista duunia	21		
työllistymistä	19		
oppisopimuskoulutus	14		
työllistämisehto	13		
työllistämisvelvoite	11		
oppisopimuskoulutettavat	7		
palkkatukeen	2		

Table 2. Feature importance based on random forest algorithm

Employment criteria		SME criteria	
Importance	Feature	Importance	Feature
0,24395	palkkatukityöllistämisen kuvaus	0,413793337	jaettu
0,13825	työllistäminen	0,172509368	mikroyritys
0,12865	työllistämisen	0,169345486	kevennetty kilpailutus
0,10647	palkkatuki	0,135503609	pieni tai keskisuuri yritys
0,08337	palkkatukeen	0,064600499	minikilpailutus
0,05462	oppisopimuskoulutukseen	0,021872612	kertahankinta
0,04025	työllistämään	0,01398026	tilata suoraan
0,03716	tarjoamaan työpaikan	0,005520088	dynaaminen toimittajarekisteri
0,03436	oikeutettuja palkkatukeen	0,002874741	tarjota yhteen
0,03272	työttömiä	0	tarjota useampaan
0,02139	työllistämistoimet	0	hankkia useammalta tuottajalta
0,01950	oppisopimuskoulutettavat	0	aliurakoitsija
0,01432	työllistymistä		
0,01399	oikeutettu palkkatukeen		
0,01389	työttömiksi työnhakijoiksi		
0,00549	työttömäksi työnhakijaksi		
0,00538	työllistämisehto		
0,00243	oppisopimuskoulutus		
0,00241	hankinnoista duunia		
0,00139	työllistämisvelvoite		